

Few-Shot Transfer Learning for Trust Score Calculation in Industrial IoT Devices

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Abstract—The Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) is revolutionizing industries by enabling seamless connectivity and automation. However, the dynamic and distributed nature of IIoT networks poses significant challenges in ensuring the trustworthiness of devices, especially during onboarding with limited data. Traditional trust management methods often require extensive historical data, making them unsuitable for newly added devices with minimal information. To address this challenge, we propose a novel few-shot transfer learning approach for trust score calculation in IIoT environments. Our method leverages pre-training on probabilistic trust scores generated from a Markov Chain model, followed by fine-tuning with few-shot learning on real-world data. We evaluate the approach using three machine learning models: Random Forest, XGBoost, and Linear Regression, demonstrating that Random Forest outperforms the others in the few-shot scenario. We also analyze the computational complexity and energy consumption of the models to provide insights into the trade-offs between predictive performance, resource usage, and environmental impact. This work contributes a new perspective on trust management in IIoT, paving the way for more adaptive and data-efficient solutions.

Index Terms—Few-shot learning, Transfer learning, Industrial IoT, Trust score, Random Forest, XGBoost.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) is transforming industries by enabling real-time monitoring and automation of complex processes. In this interconnected environment, ensuring the trustworthiness of devices is paramount for maintaining the security, reliability, and efficiency of IIoT systems. Trust management (TM) mechanisms evaluate the behaviour of devices to establish their reliability in the network, typically by calculating a trust score. This score is used to make critical decisions such as allowing device access to certain resources or excluding potentially compromised devices from the network. One of the key challenges in trust management for IIoT is the onboarding of new devices with limited data. When a device is newly added to the network, data concerning its behavior is often scarce, making it difficult to accurately predict its trustworthiness. This situation presents a few-shot learning problem, where a model must be able to learn effectively from a small number of labeled samples. Given that IIoT environments are dynamic and data availability is often limited, predicting trust scores for new devices becomes crucial for maintaining system

security and operational integrity. In this paper, we address the problem of trust score prediction for newly onboarded devices in IIoT networks. Existing methods for trust score calculation, such as those based on traditional machine learning or statistical models, typically require extensive historical data, which may not always be available. As a result, these models may struggle to generalize to devices with minimal or partial data, leading to suboptimal predictions that can impact the overall system security. To tackle these challenges, we propose a few-shot transfer learning approach for trust score calculation. Our approach leverages pre-training on trust scores generated from a Markov Chain model, which captures probabilistic trust assessments based on the evolving risk and reputation states of IIoT devices. The pre-trained model is then fine-tuned with a few real-world data samples from newly onboarded devices, enabling it to adapt its learned knowledge and make accurate trust predictions. We implement and evaluate this approach using three machine learning models: Random Forest, XGBoost, and Linear Regression, providing a comparative analysis of their performance. The main contributions of this paper are:

- We propose a novel few-shot transfer learning framework for trust score calculation in IIoT, designed to work with minimal data for newly onboarded devices.
- We conduct a comparative evaluation of three machine learning models Random Forest, XGBoost, and Linear Regression—to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach.
- We assess the computational complexity and energy consumption of the models, providing insights into the trade-offs between predictive performance and resource usage.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews the related work, Section III outlines the methodology used in this study, Section IV presents the results and analysis, and Section V discusses the findings. Finally, Section VI concludes the paper and suggests future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Trust management (TM) in IIoT has been an important topic due to the need for reliable communication among

connected devices. The literature on trust score calculation can be divided into traditional methods and machine learning-based approaches.

A. Trust Score Calculation in IIoT

Traditional trust calculation methods in IIoT often involve techniques like Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM), Dempster-Shafer Theory (DST) [1], or graph-based models. For instance, an MCDM-based approach combined with a Deep Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network has been used to calculate trust scores based on metrics such as packet loss, delay, and throughput [2]. Another approach utilised graph exploration algorithms to compute trust scores in large-scale IoT networks by modelling the network as a trust relationship graph, where nodes represent devices and edges represent trust levels between them [3]. While these approaches offer a baseline for trust calculation, they typically require extensive data collection and aggregation, making them less effective in dynamic and data-scarce IIoT environments.

B. Few-Shot Learning in IIoT

Few-shot learning [4] is a promising approach for IIoT trust calculation because it addresses the problem of data scarcity in newly established networks. Most existing IIoT networks require large datasets to train reliable models, which is not always feasible in real-world scenarios. Few-shot learning has been explored in various IoT contexts, particularly for anomaly detection and classification tasks [5], where it allows models to learn from a limited number of examples. However, its application in trust score prediction remains relatively unexplored. The need for effective trust models that can predict a device's trustworthiness with minimal data makes few-shot learning an attractive solution [6].

C. Machine Learning for Trust Calculation

The application of machine learning techniques to the field of trust management in the context of the Internet of Things (IoT) has gained significant traction in recent times, largely due to their capacity to predict future trustworthiness based on an analysis of historical data and the observed behaviour of devices. Previous research has employed a range of techniques, including Support Vector Machines (SVMs), Autoencoders, and LightGBM, for the detection of anomalies and the calculation of trust scores [7]. Other studies have employed a combination of techniques, including Bayesian learning, blockchain-based approaches, and federated learning, to address security concerns and develop privacy-preserving trust management solutions for IIoT networks [8]. However, these machine-learning models frequently necessitate the utilisation of extensive datasets for training purposes and may exhibit a lack of generalisability about new or previously unencountered devices. A review of the literature reveals a notable absence of research applying few-shot learning techniques for trust score calculation in IIoT contexts. This highlights the potential value

of integrating few-shot learning with machine learning-based trust models to address the limitations associated with data availability and adaptability in dynamic environments.

D. Summary of Related Work

- **Trust Score Calculation in IIoT:** Traditional methods use MCDM, graph-based models, and DST but struggle with scalability and adaptability in dynamic environments.
- **Few-Shot Learning in IIoT:** Presents a viable approach to deal with data scarcity, but its application in trust calculation remains limited.
- **Machine Learning for Trust Calculation:** Machine learning has shown promise, but data requirements and generalisability issues suggest a need for integrating few-shot learning to fill the gap.

This section thus establishes the motivation for leveraging few-shot transfer learning in the context of IIoT trust score calculation, providing a foundation for the proposed methodology.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section describes the few-shot transfer learning process stages for IIoT trust score prediction, including dataset preparation, model training, and evaluation metrics. The entire process is illustrated in Figure 1. The architecture of the proposed system is shown in Figure 2.

A. Step 1: Pre-Training for Few-Shot Transfer Learning

The few-shot transfer learning model starts with *pre-training* using trust scores generated from a Markov Chain model, as discussed in our previous work [9]. The Markov Chain model provides probabilistic trust scores based on the evolving risk and reputation states of IIoT devices. These scores train a base model (Random Forest, XGBoost, or Linear Regression) that learns how device features correlate with trustworthiness. This step creates a foundation for knowledge transfer when real-world device data is limited.

B. Step 2: Fine-Tuning with Few-Shot Learning

Once the base model has been pre-trained, it is *fine-tuned* using a small set of real device data through few-shot learning. The fine-tuning process adjusts the model to better handle the nuances of real-world data. The limited number of labeled samples from newly onboarded devices allows the model to adapt its learned knowledge and make accurate predictions for trust scores in production environments.

C. Step 3: Dataset and Features

The dataset used for model training and evaluation comprises several key features related to device performance and security. These include:

- **CPU Utilization:** The percentage of processing power being used by the device.
- **RAM Utilization:** The proportion of memory in use.

Fig. 1: Activity diagram illustrating the overall process flow of the few-shot transfer learning methodology.

- **Security Level:** A discrete measure reflecting the security posture of the device.
- **Packet Loss:** A feature indicating the quality of network communications.
- **Intrusion Detection System (IDS) Score:** A metric showing how well the device detects and prevents malicious activities.

These features are used as inputs to the machine learning models to predict the trust scores.

D. Step 4: Trust Score Calculation (Piecewise Function)

The *trust score* for each device is computed using a *piecewise function*, which reflects the relationship between the features and the overall trustworthiness. The trust score is influenced by the *risk state*, *reputation state*, and *IDS performance*:

$$T = \begin{cases} \max(0, 50 - w_R \times R + w_{Rep} \times Rep + w_I \times I) & \text{if } R \geq 4 \\ \min(100, 80 - w_R \times R + w_{Rep} \times Rep + w_I \times I) & \text{if } R \leq 2 \\ \max(20, 70 - w_R \times R + w_{Rep} \times Rep + w_I \times I) & \text{if } 2 < R < 4 \end{cases}$$

Fig. 2: System architecture diagram illustrating the different layers involved in the few-shot transfer learning process for trust score calculation.

Where:

- R is the risk state,
- Rep is the reputation state,
- I is the IDS score.

This piecewise function reflects the real-time status of the device and adjusts the trust score accordingly, assigning higher weights to more critical security and operational factors.

E. Step 5: Machine Learning Models

Three models were used to predict the trust scores of IIoT devices:

- **Random Forest (RF):** An ensemble learning method that creates multiple decision trees during training and averages their outputs. Random Forest captures non-linear relationships and performs well with tabular data.
- **XGBoost:** A gradient boosting decision tree model that improves accuracy iteratively by correcting errors in weak learners. It is known for its speed and high predictive power.
- **Linear Regression:** A simple model that assumes a linear relationship between input features and the target (trust

score). While it is computationally efficient, it lacks the flexibility of tree-based models for capturing complex relationships.

The models were fine-tuned using few-shot learning to adapt to the limited real-world data available.

F. Step 6: Evaluation Metrics

To evaluate the model performance, we used the following regression metrics:

- **Mean Squared Error (MSE):** Measures the average squared difference between predicted and actual trust scores. The formula is:

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2$$

- **R-squared (R^2):** Measures the proportion of the variance in trust scores that is explained by the model:

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE):** Represents the average absolute difference between predicted and actual trust scores:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\hat{y}_i - y_i|$$

- **Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE):** The square root of MSE, providing an interpretable measure of prediction accuracy:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\hat{y}_i - y_i)^2}$$

These metrics provide a comprehensive evaluation of the model's performance, focusing on error magnitude and the model's ability to explain the variance in trust scores.

IV. RESULTS

In this section, we present the results of applying few-shot transfer learning to predict trust scores of IIoT devices using Random Forest, XGBoost, and Linear Regression models. We also discuss the model complexity, energy consumption, and feature importance using SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) [10].

A. Model Performance

To assess the performance of the models, we used metrics such as Mean Squared Error (MSE), R^2 score, Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE). Table I summarises the results for all three models.

The results demonstrate that Random Forest consistently performs better than XGBoost and Linear Regression across all metrics. The MSE of the Random Forest model is the lowest, indicating that it has the least squared error on average. The MAE of 5.94 for Random Forest indicates that the model's

TABLE I: Performance Metrics for Few-Shot Transfer Learning Models

Model	MSE	R^2	MAE	RMSE
Random Forest	64.90	0.752	5.94	8.06
XGBoost	75.04	0.713	6.38	8.66
Linear Regression	95.28	0.636	7.86	9.76

TABLE II: Cross-Validation R^2 Scores for Few-Shot Transfer Learning Models

Model	Average R^2	Cross-Validation R^2 Scores
Random Forest	0.997	[0.997, 0.996, 0.996, 0.997, 0.996]
XGBoost	0.998	[0.998, 0.998, 0.998, 0.998, 0.998]
Linear Regression	0.724	[0.723, 0.725, 0.721, 0.735, 0.712]

average error is approximately 5.94 trust score units, which is lower than that observed for the other models. The RMSE of 8.06 indicates that the discrepancies observed in Random Forest are comparatively minor in comparison to those observed in XGBoost (RMSE of 8.66) and Linear Regression (RMSE of 9.76). XGBoost demonstrates comparable performance, although it exhibits a higher MAE of 6.38 and a higher RMSE of 8.66 compared to Random Forest. The slightly higher values for XGBoost indicate that, while it performs well, it produces larger errors on average and exhibits greater variability in error magnitude. As anticipated, linear regression exhibits the poorest performance across all metrics, with an MSE of 95.28 and an MAE of 7.86. The elevated RMSE of 9.76 for linear regression signifies that its predictions are characterised by more pronounced errors, particularly in comparison to the non-linear tree-based models.

B. Cross-Validation Performance

To ensure the robustness of the models, we performed 5-fold cross-validation. The average R^2 scores across all folds are presented in Table II.

Both Random Forest and XGBoost achieved near-perfect cross-validation performance, with average R^2 scores of 0.997 and 0.998, respectively, suggesting high generalization capability. Linear Regression, as expected, demonstrated lower generalization ability with an average R^2 score of 0.724.

C. Model Complexity

Table 3 presents the complexity of each model, measured in terms of the number of trees, total nodes, and average tree depth for Random Forest and XGBoost, and the number of parameters for Linear Regression.

TABLE III: Model Complexity

Model	Num. of Trees	Total Nodes	Av. Tree Depth
Random Forest	100	2164	5.39
XGBoost	100	1064	6
Linear Regression	N/A	N/A	N/A

The Random Forest model has more total nodes (2164) than XGBoost (1064), but its average tree depth (5.39) is slightly shallower compared to XGBoost’s depth (6). This suggests that Random Forest may produce shallower, wider trees, while XGBoost tends to produce deeper, narrower trees. The deeper trees in XGBoost may allow it to capture more nuanced relationships, but this comes at a higher computational cost. Linear Regression has the simplest structure with only 10 parameters, corresponding to the number of features plus an intercept term. This simplicity makes it computationally efficient, but it lacks the ability to model complex non-linear relationships that are better handled by tree-based models.

D. Energy Consumption and Environmental Impact

In terms of energy consumption, the values tracked using CodeCarbon [11] were extremely low, with negligible energy usage and CO2 emissions. This highlights the efficiency of the few-shot transfer learning approach, particularly when using the Random Forest model, which balances high predictive performance with minimal computational cost. While XGBoost offers slightly higher complexity, its computational footprint remains similarly low, making both models feasible for real-time IIoT environments.

E. Feature Importance Analysis

To interpret the predictions of the models, we used SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) to measure the contribution of each feature to the predicted trust scores. The SHAP values quantify how much each feature increases or decreases the predicted trust score, helping us understand the importance of each feature. Figure 3 shows the SHAP summary plots for Random Forest and XGBoost.

In the Random Forest model (Figure 3a) the device features *RiskState*, *SecurityLevel* and *PacketLoss* emerge as the most influential. Higher *RiskState* and *PacketLoss* decrease the trust score (negative SHAP values), while higher *SecurityLevel* improves it. In the XGBoost model (Figure 3b), While *RiskState* and *SecurityLevel* remain important, *OSInverted* and *PackagesInverted* also play significant roles in determining the trust score. Devices with more up-to-date software (high *OSInverted* and *PackagesInverted*) receive higher trust scores.

The SHAP analysis confirms that domain knowledge-based key features, like *RiskState* and *SecurityLevel*, are very important in figuring out trust scores, while features like *PacketLoss* always have a negative effect. This analysis provides transparency into the models, demonstrating how they map device features to trust scores.

V. DISCUSSION

A. Strengths of Few-Shot Learning

The proposed few-shot transfer learning approach demonstrates significant potential in addressing the challenges associated with trust score calculation in IIoT environments where data availability is limited. By leveraging pre-training on trust

scores generated from a Markov Chain model, the approach effectively transfers knowledge to the few-shot learning phase, allowing the model to adapt to newly onboarded devices with minimal data. This is particularly advantageous for IIoT scenarios, where rapid device onboarding and dynamic environments make it difficult to gather large datasets for model training. Random Forest and XGBoost emerged as effective models for this few-shot learning approach due to their ability to handle nonlinear relationships and interactions between features. Both models employ tree-based ensemble methods that capture complex dependencies within the data, which are often present in IIoT trust metrics (e.g., risk state, CPU utilization). Their performance indicates that few-shot learning, when combined with tree-based models, can effectively learn from limited data, providing accurate trust predictions in IIoT settings.

B. Limitations of Few-Shot Learning

While the few-shot transfer learning approach provides substantial benefits for IIoT trust management, it is not without limitations. A key requirement for few-shot learning is the need for pre-training, which involves training a base model on trust scores derived from a Markov Chain model or other statistical methods. This step introduces a dependency on the quality of the pre-training data, which can influence the effectiveness of the model. Additionally, few-shot learning still relies on having a small yet representative subset of labeled data for fine-tuning. If the available subset is not diverse enough, the model may struggle to generalize to new device types or novel situations.

C. Insights from Model Comparison

The comparative analysis reveals that Random Forest consistently outperforms Linear Regression and XGBoost in the few-shot learning scenario. The superior performance of Random Forest can be attributed to its robustness to overfitting when working with small datasets and its ability to handle noisy or imperfect data, which is common in IIoT environments. While XGBoost also performs well, its reliance on iterative boosting may make it less effective with very limited data compared to Random Forest’s bagging approach.

Linear Regression, on the other hand, exhibited the poorest performance due to its assumption of a linear relationship between the input features and the trust score. In IIoT, where device behaviors and trust relationships are often nonlinear and complex, linear models are less capable of capturing the underlying patterns in the data.

D. Impact of Computational Footprint and Resource Usage

In real-world applications, the choice of machine learning model must also consider the computational footprint and resource usage. While few-shot learning allows for rapid adaptation with minimal data, the energy consumption and training time can vary across models. Random Forest, for example, involves training multiple decision trees, which can increase resource requirements compared to linear models. However,

(a) SHAP summary plot for Random Forest

(b) SHAP summary plot for XGBoost

Fig. 3: SHAP value comparison for feature importance in Random Forest and XGBoost models

the trade-off between resource usage and prediction accuracy is justified in IIoT scenarios where ensuring the security and reliability of the network is of utmost importance. Tracking the energy consumption using tools such as CodeCarbon provided valuable insights into the environmental impact of the models. Although the overall energy consumption for training was relatively low, the results emphasize the importance of considering resource efficiency, especially for deployment in large-scale IIoT networks where multiple models may need to be maintained.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we addressed the challenge of calculating trust scores for newly onboarded IIoT devices with limited data. The proposed few-shot transfer learning approach combines pre-training on trust scores derived from a Markov Chain model with fine-tuning using few-shot learning techniques on real-world data. This method enables accurate trust score predictions despite the scarcity of labeled samples, thereby enhancing the reliability and security of IIoT networks. Our comparative evaluation of three machine learning models—Random Forest, XGBoost, and Linear Regression—demonstrated the superiority of tree-based models (Random Forest and XGBoost) in terms of prediction accuracy. The results also highlighted the importance of hyperparameter tuning and cross-validation for optimizing model performance. Additionally, the analysis of the computational footprint and energy consumption emphasized the need to balance prediction accuracy with resource efficiency, particularly for large-scale IIoT deployments. Future work will explore extending this approach to incorporate additional features, such as adaptive risk assessment and device behavior profiling. We also aim to investigate more advanced transfer learning techniques and hybrid models to further improve trust management in IIoT. This research lays the foundation for developing data-efficient and adaptive trust management systems capable of addressing the unique challenges posed by IIoT environments.

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